

GANGRENOUS CHOLECYSTITIS- AN UNCOMMON PRESENTATION

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Abstract

Introduction: Gangrenous cholecystitis (GC) is the most severe form of acute cholecystitis, a type of acute inflammation of the gallbladder and is potentially fatal complication of acute cholecystitis. It occurs when prolonged and severe inflammation causes increased pressure in the gallbladder, leading to reduced blood flow and gangrene. The symptoms overlap with acute cholecystitis but are often more severe. There can be right upper quadrant abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting, fever with leucocytosis.

Case Report: We report a sixty-year-old male, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with yellowish discoloration of sclera and passage of dark yellow urine for last one week which was associated with mild itching and pain abdomen. His ultrasonogram showed calculi of 5 mm in neck of gall bladder with prostatomegaly. The MRCP showed multiple simple hepatic cysts with grossly distended gall bladder measuring 12.2 x 4 cm with multiple small calculi in lumen and 6x4 mm calculi at neck. The gall bladder showed diffuse oedematous, circumferential thickening measuring 7 mm with mucosal irregularity and diffusion restriction, possibility of gangrenous cholecystitis. There was mild perihepatic and peri-splenic free fluid with bilateral minimal pleural effusion. Pancreas showed diffuse fatty replacement. There were few subcentimetric lymph nodes in peri portal, para-aortic, para cavernal location, largest measuring 8 mm in short axis diameter in peri portal location. In view of gangrenous cholecystitis, patient underwent urgent laparoscopic cholecystectomy with histopathological examination of removed gall bladder in which findings of MRCP were confirmed. Patient post-operative period was event free and he was discharged under haemodynamically stable condition after three days.

Conclusion: Acute gangrenous cholecystitis has an increased mortality. Male and older patients with comorbidities such as diabetes and coronary artery disease are at higher risk of developing this disease. One should be more vigil for uncommon presentations as it is well said that stich in time saves nine.

Keywords: Cholelithiasis, Cholecystitis, Gangrenous, Ultrasonogram, MRCP, Jaundice

Introduction- Gangrenous cholecystitis (GC) is the most severe form of acute cholecystitis, a type of acute inflammation of the gallbladder and is potentially fatal complication of acute cholecystitis. It occurs when prolonged and severe inflammation causes increased pressure in the gallbladder, leading to reduced blood flow and gangrene. The symptoms overlap with acute cholecystitis but are often more severe. There can be right upper quadrant abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting, fever with leucocytosis. The risk factors are older age group (often over 45-70 years old), diabetes mellitus, heart disease, male gender, delayed admission to the hospital. The complications are perforation of the gallbladder leading to widespread infection. The diagnosis is challenging due to nonspecific symptoms, but imaging tests like ultrasound, MRCP and CT scans confirm the diagnosis. It is a surgical emergency and requires prompt cholecystectomy. Laparoscopic surgery may be possible, but open surgery may be necessary in some cases. Gangrenous cholecystitis is a dangerous complication of cholecystitis that necessitates urgent surgical intervention to prevent life-threatening outcomes. It can have some uncommon presentation like short duration of jaundice, as in our present case, in which early recognition is must because it safeguards patient from going into

sepsis and multi organ failure which can increase morbidity as well as mortality. Moreover, it also saves finances by decreasing the need of prolonged duration of management in intensive care unit.

Case Report- We report a sixty-year-old male, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with yellowish discolouration of sclera and passage of dark yellow urine for last one week which was associated with mild itching and pain abdomen. There was no history of fever, passage of clay-coloured stools, haematemesis, melena, joint pains, ascites, pedal edema. On clinical examination he was having icterus but rest of generalized physical examination, chest, cardiovascular, per abdominal and neurological examination was essentially normal. On evaluation, his first complete hemogram showed microcytic hypochromic anaemia (Hb 6.6%) thrombocytopenia (97,000), normal total leucocyte count ($8,000 \text{ mm}^3$) with increased AST and ALT levels (153 & 179 I.U. respectively), mild hyperbilirubinemia (2 mg%) with normal total serum protein & albumin levels (7.2 gm and 3.6 gm respectively). The repeat liver function test after gap of two days showed increased serum bilirubin level of 5.8 mg% with normal alkaline phosphatase levels. The renal function test, thyroid profile, blood sugar, serum electrolytes, ECG, Chest X-ray, urine complete examination, HbsAg, anti HCV & anti-HIV antibody were negative. His ultrasonogram showed calculi of 5 mm in neck of gall bladder with prostatomegaly. The MRCP showed multiple simple hepatic cysts with grossly distended gall bladder measuring 12.2 x 4 cm with multiple small calculi in lumen and 6x4 mm calculi at neck. The gall bladder showed diffuse oedematous, circumferential thickening measuring 7 mm with mucosal irregularity and diffusion restriction, possibility of gangrenous cholecystitis. There was mild perihepatic and peri-splenic free fluid with bilateral minimal pleural effusion. Pancreas showed diffuse fatty replacement. There were few subcentemetric lymph nodes in peri portal, para-aortic, para cavernal location, largest measuring 8 mm in short axis diameter in peri portal location. In view of gangrenous cholecystitis, patient underwent urgent laparoscopic cholecystectomy with histopathological examination of removed gall bladder in which findings of MRCP were confirmed. Patient post-operative period was event free and he was discharged under haemodynamically stable condition after three days.

FIGURE 1- MRCP Showing concentrically thickened and dilated gall bladder

FIGURE 2-MRCP Showing grossly dilated gall bladder with normal hepatic ducts and CBD

FIGURE 3-MRCP Showing grossly dilated gall bladder with stones in lumen and neck causing gangrenous changes.

Discussion- Acute gangrenous cholecystitis (AGC) is a medical emergency that carries high morbidity and results from compromised perfusion of the gallbladder wall secondary to increased intraluminal pressure because of the persistent complete or partial obstruction of the cystic duct [1]. Compared with cholecystitis without necrosis (CN), development of acute gangrenous cholecystitis in patients can negatively impact outcome [2]. The presence of acute gangrenous cholecystitis results in increased morbidity and mortality especially in elderly patients [3]. Previous studies have suggested that early diagnosis and treatment could decrease the rate of complications [4]. To date, however, there are no defined guidelines available for triage of these patients to early surgical treatment [4]. Preoperative risk factors evaluated included age, sex, diabetes, preoperative hypotension (defined as systolic blood pressure [SBP] less than 100), preoperative diagnosis of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), weight, and admission laboratory work including serum lactate and total bilirubin. Logistic regression factors such as diabetes, CAD, and SIRS were found to be predictive of acute gangrenous cholecystitis [5]. In a multicentre, randomized, double-blind, controlled trial, [6] laparoscopic cholecystectomy was found to be safe in patients with acute gangrenous cholecystitis. Other studies quote a conversion rate for acute gangrenous cholecystitis to be higher than that of uncomplicated acute cholecystitis [7,8]. Some studies have observed a similar population of older male patients being more affected by acute gangrenous cholecystitis, often with an elevation in preoperative bilirubin [9,10]. Our case was different in a way that jaundice is uncommon presentation of gangrenous cholecystitis and usually AGC presents with pain abdomen & features of SIRS but in our case the main presentation was of short duration jaundice & pain abdomen which was mild and non-specific. There was no history of fever or SIRS but suddenly increasing serum bilirubin with low haemoglobin and platelet count gave hint of hibernating gangrenous cholecystitis. Moreover, in old age, sometimes the responses in form of frank SIRS are blunt. In our case

there were two risk factors i.e. old age and male sex. This anticipation of some complication in view of gall stone at neck forced for urgent MRCP and confirming the findings of AGC.

Conclusion- Acute gangrenous cholecystitis has an increased mortality. Male and older patients with comorbidities such as diabetes and coronary artery disease are at higher risk of developing this disease. The development of SIRS and an increased bilirubin should alarm for the possibility of acute gangrenous cholecystitis. One should be more vigilant for uncommon presentations as it is well said that stich in time saves nine.

Conflict of Interest - The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest and no funding was taken from any source to conduct this research. The consent was taken from the patient and family members before publication of this paper.

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